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FRANCE ON THE EVE OF THE WORLD ECONOMIC CRISIS OF 1900-1903

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Abstract

The years 1900-1903 were remembered as the years of the world crisis. The ruin of small and medium-sized enterprises led to massive job closures and, consequently, mass strikes. All over the world there was an increase in prices for manufactured products and in general economic life deteriorated.

Many manufacturing plants were closed. The price of industrial products fell below the cost of the product. The number of unemployed in large cities has increased. France was affected by the global economic crisis. As a result of the economic policy of the French government, the crisis caused less damage to the country's economy. In general, the impact of the crisis was less felt in France.

Keywords: General world economic crisis, Monopolies, Capital, Bonds, Industry

The economic crisis of 1900-1903 was accompanied by the financial bankruptcy of a number of enterprises and a sharp drop in the level of production. The economic crisis had a negative impact on the economy of most developed countries. Heper development of the industry as well as the emergence of many large companies and syndicates can be cited as the cause of the crisis. On the eve of the world economic crisis, the internal situation in France was unstable. Replacing each other, governments could not cope with the desires of the population. On that Eve, the people were in search of new Hungarians[15.66]. Freycine appointed general Boulanger as Minister of war. He was a former right-wing Republican for personal gain. At first, his colleagues saw Boulanger as harmless. But he was prone to lavish presentations. The June 1886 law prohibited people from living in the territory of the Republic who had previously been in power in France. Also, they were not allowed to occupy official state positions in the absence of participation in the elections. This law did not apply to aristocrats who until that time served in the army. Boulanger, in contrast to the legislator, excluded from the command Divisional general Duke Omalsky and Colonel of the 7th CA Alry Rifle Regiment Duke Chartres from his list. This event created the great ajyataj all attention was focused on Boulanger. In addition, he would carry out radical reforms in the army to improve the food and housing conditions of those soldiers. He sided with the privates during controversial events with the military administration. The Buddha led to the rapid growth of his fame the public warmly applauded Boulanger, who passed the military parade on the day of July 14[17.42]. The occupation policy of England and Italy in Egypt and Tunisia strained relations with France. There were tensions at the border with the Bismarck government. In the border areas with Germany, an sra officer was accused of spying for Germany and was involved in the investigations. Obsessed with the struggle against the clergy and

monarchists, the Republicans did not immediately notice how a new political force, the nationalist movement, was growing and gaining strength. Its rise is partly associated with the general rise of political radicalism, caused by the disillusionment of the bulk of the population with the results of the policy of "moderate Republicans". The rapid development of nationalism was due to the fact that French society could not come to terms with the occupation of Alsace and Lorraine by Germany. Military excitement over the small incident on the Franco-German border in 1886-1887 fueled vengeful and militaristic sentiments, in which the nationalist movement intensified in France. Nationalists who criticized many of the decisions of the Third Republic governments gradually began to deny the constitutional foundations of the Third Republic. They urged not to openly recognize the laws of the Republic, seeing parliamentarism as the main reason for the weakening of state power and national unity. Nationalists were demanding a revision of the Constitution to strengthen executive power through the presidential republic of 1848[14,250]. General of revenge". This is how the nationalists called general Boulanger.

The firm determination that he demonstrated in 1887 in the face of German threats made him the idol of the crowd – the "general of revenge." Various political groups tried to use Genral for their own political interests. However, the main supporters of Genral were considered members of the "Patriotic League". by the mid-eighties, this organization had more than 180 thousand members. In March 1888, Boulanger was discharged from the army. In the early elections, he ran for the Chamber of Deputies and won. Boulanger addressed an appeal to Parliament to make amendments and additions to the Constitution. However, the parliamentarians did not accept his proposal. At that time, elections were held on the basis of party lists, and the law allowed the same person to be nominated more than once in different circles. Boulanger took advantage of

this by participating in re-elections in various neighborhoods in the second half of 1888 under the slogans of dissolving Parliament, changing the Constitution and convening the Constituent Assembly, winning the entire electoral neighborhood. Boulanger won the elections before his time, but did not dare to seize the state by force [19.54]. The Republican deputies enacted the law on the party list. After that, one candidate could not nominate himself from a different precinct several times. Concerned about political persecution, Boulanger moved to Brussels. After a while, he returned there. Following Boulanger's death, the Nationalist Movement lost its former popularity. Beginning in 1876, workers' congresses began to be convened. At the Workers' Congress in 1880, the Socialists of France achieved the creation of the Workers' Party. However, the Workers' Party soon disintegrated. A significant number of journalists, writers and politicians appeared who declared themselves "independent Socialists". They understood socialism broadly as a policy of reforms aimed at establishing more just relations in society. "Along with the Socialists, trade unions began to form in the organization. Representatives of the social movement were not represented in Parliament [14.289]. However, after the incident that went down in history as the "panama scandal", the situation changed. In the same incident, the name of a very high-ranking official was mentioned in a bribery scandal. In 1891, an investigation into the Panama company became public. The Panama had a great repercussion in the country up to half of the deputies in parliament resigned. In the elections in 1893, the Socialists won many Deputy seats in Parliament for the first time in their history. The liberal-moderate alliance in parliament made it possible to form a strong government for the first time in the history of the Third Republic. This situation continued until the end of the 90s. Their main motto: "calm, tolerance, practical reform!" it was. The Socialists took a break from their struggle against the Catholic Church. The moderate liberal Alliance carried out a series of reforms. In 1892, a law was passed to compensate workers for the loss of health during work, in 1898 a law was passed limiting the working day to 10 hours for adolescents and 11 hours for women. In the moderate Republic, in turn, they carried out reforms of the state, which ensured the interest of business circles. Such development led to the creation of a progressive faction of progressive supporters from among the moderate Republicans. In the early 90s. The progressives faced an unprecedented wave of political terror. In March 1892, in Paris, a bomb set by the anarchist Ravachol was detonated in one of the restaurants. This was followed by explosions in many residential buildings. Despite the fact that he was arrested and executed, terrorist activities continued. Such anarchist events caused panic among the population of the capital. In December 1893, a left-wing radical named Auguste Vaillant dropped a bomb in the meeting room of the Chamber of Deputies. Such terrorist attacks were skillfully used by the left-wing press in an anti-government campaign. From 1893 to 1894, parliament passed an amnesty resolution on the press in an attempt to end terrorism and anarchy. These decisions were followed by the adoption of a law providing for

the criminal prosecution of representatives of the press, who called on people to terror and anarchy [14.287]. On the basis of the law on criminal prosecution of crimes occurring in the field of press on the court of jurors came into force. Left-wing jurists disagreed with the new laws adopted and saw these laws as a violation of the people's rights and freedoms. In the 70s of the XIX century, France had already completed the Industrial Revolution. In France, the fields of chemical metallurgy, various mechanical engineering and paper processing were more developed. Various household items, looms, textile products, weapons and other products produced from this period were produced with the application of new technological means. Despite these enumerations, the industrialization process of France was not fully completed. Large industrial centers were concentrated mainly in large cities. Agriculture was still considered the leading sector of the economy due to the number of people employed and the country's income from the products produced. Towards the end of the nineteenth century, agriculture in France was going through a severe crisis. The main reason for this crisis was the inability to compete with cheap agricultural products from the United States and Canada. Cheap grain exported from the USA and bankrupt farmers, large landowners, land tenants in France. The country has lost its prospects for grain growing in the field of Agriculture. But earlier the most profitable area of Agriculture was grain growing. At that time, another branch of Agriculture was experiencing a crisis in winemaking.

In the country there was an epidemic of phylloxera, which destroyed grape trees. Hundreds of thousands of hectares of vineyards perished. The shortage of raw materials for the production of wine was aggravated [15.85]. Such negative processes in the field of Agriculture have reduced the profitability of Agriculture in France as a whole. As a result of this, the demand for industrial goods decreased due to the extremely low purchasing power among the population. As a result, the price of industrial goods fell. Annual economic development had weakened. There was no increase in the population in the country, as the ratio of newborns and deaths between people was equalized. On the eve of the crisis, investment in industry and real estate decreased. As a result of this, commodities invested capital mainly in bonds issued by the state. One of the main reasons for this is that in France, governments recognized the debt of each year, which reduced the risk of losing the capital invested in the bonds of the state to a minimum. The second main reason is that bondholders are not afraid of the risk of inflation. Because the Golden Parity of France, which Napoleon I had introduced since 1803, remained unchanged. Such stability of France continued for more than a hundred years until 1914 [14.293]. Such a financial policy of the French government, justifying the eyes of depositors, caused sharp budget deficits in government spending. The French government tried to compensate for such deficits at the expense of external debt. French investors did not buy French bonds alone. They put a large amount of capital into their bonds in a bunch of neighboring countries cooperating with the

French government . On the eve of the crisis, the French government made some changes to the foreign trade strategy . In previous periods, the foreign policy of France was based on the principle of international exchange . However, the rapid decline in the prices of industrial products in the countries of the world prompted the government to implement the policy of protectionism . Already since 1892, customs duties began to be increased . This trend continued until 1910 . Protectionism policy led to the fact that the country's economy came out with less damage from the destructive effects of the crisis .Economic growth was observed in the country . The policy of protectionism had a negative impact on economic development . The quality of the products produced in the country decreased due to the importation of foreign products, because the risk of not being able to compete with the products produced abroad has disappeared . Therefore, the introduction of new technologies into the industry has weakened . Because of this, the industrial products of France could not compete in the foreign market with the industrial products of other neighboring countries . In addition, sanahe businesses across the country quickly became cartelized . The cartels signed agreements on maintaining high price increases . Buddha reduced the accessibility of industrial products . In the mid-90s, noticeable development began to be observed in the industry . Even in later periods, between 1905 and 1914, economic growth was 5% per annum .The achievement of this result was caused by the government's policy on capital investment . however, it should be noted in private investittsyan invested in the country's economy . France achieved such an economic rating only on the eve of the Second Empire . Apparently, various economic programs financed by the state ensured the economy's exit from the crisis . In the quarter of the nineteenth century, France was known as a trendsetter . At that time, Paris attracted writers, poet artists and thinkers from all parts of the world . The main reason for the creation of such a fertile literary environment was the creative possibilities provided by the Third Republic yi azadsensurate[9.21] . At this time, new lines of artistic art appear in France . from there it spread all over the world . In the last quarter of the XIX century, a new artistic Impressionism was created, which was considered a bright expression of the stylistic diversity of French art . The Impressionists were able to express themselves in a broader sense in the field of painting . The leader of the field of Impressionist painters was considered Kold Mone . His painting “ the image of the rising sun ” brought the artist worldwide fame . Mone repeatedly painted a painting of the same object in the same space at different times of the day .This is how the paintings"Ronen's Hacks "and" Rouen Cathedral " were painted . at that time, Pisaro and Alfred Sisley, an English-born artist, became world famous for their paintings in the landscape genre . bi other isdedad artist Auguste Renoir he painted mostly female portirets . In the persanages painted by Auguste Renoir, they have an irresistible charm, although they do not have a pisycho-logical depth . Edgar dags mostly filmed scenes of various genres . He studied at the Academy of Arts . Edgar did not become a complete impressionist if he did not

adhere to the traditional school of painting . He painted mostly paintings of various arts of city life . Unlike other impressionists, Edgar never painted in the landscape genre .The outstanding sculptor Auguste Rodin can be considered belonging to the spirit of Impressionism like other impressionists, he strove to reflect in stone the fleeting facial expressions or postures of people. From 1880 until the end of his life, he worked on the composition “gates of Hell”, inspired by Dante's Divine Comedy[14,290] . Auguste Rodin by that time no one was able to ghersanaj managed to express his tension of thought in stone . However, the Impressionism as an artistic fine could not continue its impact on the face . The Impressionists, who fought against academic routines and innovators in art, were replaced by a group of artists united under the name “Post-Impressionists”. They did not have a common program. But each of them were brilliant artists who left a different mark on artistic art . The rapid development of industry in the early twentieth century was based on the active policy of the state . The flow of investments in all sectors of production testified to the financial health of the country, which did not experience a shortage of capital . At that time, Paris was considered the second most important (after London) financial market in the world . The most important issue facing the government was the elimination of the agrarian crisis . The development of the industry could be further stimulated if the Agra crisis disappeared . During the crisis years in France, the capacity of the domestic consumer market has noticeably increased due to the increase in real wages. At the beginning of the twentieth century, the French were quite educated as a people as a whole . The main reason for such literacy of the people was that the Third Republic sought to develop primary, secondary and higher education such measures quickly began to bear fruit . The high level of education provided the French industry with highly qualified engineers and experienced professional workers . The owners of the establishment were intellectual people . The presence of high professionalism of Engineers in the French Industry Aviation electric power generation of the national industry has become the first in the world in areas requiring high professionalism, such as mechanical engineering . At the beginning of the twentieth century, the United States was the first in the world to export cars, lagging behind in car production[14.294] . However, compared to other countries, mainly Germany and the United States, the industry of France at the end of the XI century and the beginning of the XX centuries. it was characterized by a weaker concentration of production, capital and labor. In 1906, there were 189 enterprises in France with more than a thousand employees. About a third of all workers in the country worked in enterprises with less than 10 employees. Poor concentration of production became an obstacle to the introduction of more rational methods of Labor Organization . The Buddha negatively affected the cost of the goods produced and, as a result, the selling price of the goods . For this reason, in world markets, French industrial products did not know APRA to compete with industrial products of other foreign countries . The bulk of French exports still traditionally accounted for food . In terms of dynamic

development, France was not inferior to other industrial countries at the beginning of the twentieth century, but at the end of the XIX there was a slowdown in the rapid pace of development that it had. When the French industry stagnated, the United States and Germany followed the path of rapid development in the industrial sphere, leaving France behind. [16,23] if France's share in World Trade in 1876 was 16%, then during the first World War it fell by 12%. In December 1894, a military tribunal convicted General Staff Captain Alfred Dreyfus of espionage and sentenced him to life imprisonment. However, later it turned out that the accusation was false. Dreyfus' relatives brought the case to the court of Appeal in 1897. However, in the military court, the case was not reconsidered, indicating that the material presented was insufficient. Dreyfus, a Jew by birth, was the son of an Alsatian industrial owner. Because of his nationality, the military court judges did not take the charge off Dreyfus. They saw Dreyfus as a Jew, A son of an industrialist, who did not deserve to belong to the elite of the officer corps, made up of similar aristocrats and monarchists. The actions of the military authorities were perceived by the democratic public of France as a gross violation of the elementary rights and freedoms of a citizen. As soon as Dreyfus' work became public, he created rapid ajyataj in society. Dreyfus' work has already acquired a political character, having lost the character of hiqi. In defense of the "honor of the army" and against the revision of the case, the majority of conservatives, ecclesiastical circles, as well as part of the progressives spoke out, including Melin, Dupuy and the president of the Republic Felix. However, the main supporters of the revision of the Dreyfus case were the nationalists. They called themselves "anti-Dreyfusers." After the defeat of bulangism, nationalists united around xenophobic and anti-Semitic slogans. In 1898, several nationalist organizations were formed. These organizations were mainly under Deruled's leadership, the restored League of Fatherland Parves, the French homeland League, in which intellectuals gathered. Such organizations as the anti-Semitic League, French action ("Action Française") can be cited. all these organizations had hundreds of thousands of supporters and members of all these organizations were putting pressure on the government to prevent the Dreyfus case from being reconsidered. Reconsideration of Dreyfus' case the Tartars United as Dreyfusists against the nationalists. Their main motto was the protection of the democratic rights and freedoms provided by the Republic. Under this slogan, representatives of various political forces, social movements, confessions United. They were radical soialists ,francomasons ,protesttants ,antimilitarians , anticlericals, led by jores. In early 1898, they created the Human Rights League, which played an important role in the history of the human rights movement. Seeing that the nationalist movement was becoming increasingly dangerous for statehood, most of the progressives sided with the Dreyfustists[14,289]. In 1899, prezdent Emile Loubet appointed progressive Ren H. G. Valdek Rousseau to lead the government. Representatives of all political parties were involved in the Cabinet of the new government. Socialist Alexander

Milleran was appointed Minister of trade and Industry. The government began to take decisive action against the nationalist. The leaders of the nationalists were arrested and brought to trial. In the summer of 1899, the military tribunal again convicted Captain Dreyfus during a new hearing. It was only in 1906 that Dreyfus was fully rehabilitated, while the Dreyfus affair became a catalyst for major changes in political life. First of all, the political crisis caused by him destroyed many years of efforts of conservative and liberal politicians, starting with Tyer, to create a stable political "center". At the turn of the century, almost the entire adult population of France was divided into two Druze, supporters of dreyfus and opponents of dreyfus. The confrontation between the left and right social organizations escalated. The slogan of the restoration of the monarchy among the right had already begun to lose its relevance. During the Third Republic of the left, the people's sensitivity to the idea of the protection of the Republic began to decline. At the beginning of the century, a system of organizing organized political parties was introduced in France. They combined the methods of parliamentary activity with extra-parliamentary activities. during the elections, they formed a network of local committees that communicated with voters and controlled their parliamentary factions. These changes came into force in 1901, on July 1, by the law on unions adopted at the suggestion of the valdeck-Rousseau cabinet. The adoption of this law guaranteed wide freedom of action to various associations of citizens, including political ones. The new law provided for a declarative procedure for the registration of political associations. On the eve of the 1902 parliamentary elections, several parties, mainly representing the left, began to exist legally almost simultaneously. Organizationmatya socialists began earlier than other parties. In 1901, two new socialist parties were formed. In 1901, the Republican Party of radical socialists was formed. This name reflected the desire of the organizers of the new party to unite all left-wing forces adhering to the ideal of a Democratic Republic. The desire of the radicals to cover the entire Republican part of the political spectrum alarmed the "moderate Republicans" who joined the Dreyfusard camp. At the end of 1901, they formed a Democratic Alliance, which included Louis Bartou, Raymond Poiankare, Joseph Kayliau, Alexander Ribot and others. The alliance strengthened its right flank, becoming one of the main parties in the ruling Republican majority. In 1902, the elections to the Chamber of Deputies were won by the left, who achieved the election of 350 deputies, of which 210 were radical and radical socialists, 95 were left-wing Republicans (members of the Democratic Alliance), and 45 were socialist reformers. The right-wing received 230 deputy mandates, of which 115 belonged to right-wing Republicans, 60 to nationalists, and 55 to conservatives. After the 1902 elections, the left-wing parties organized a "delegation of the left", a kind of coordination center in Parliament. The coalition formed in this way was called the "Left Bloc". The formation of the Cabinet of ministers was entrusted to Emile comb. The government considered the fight against clericalism to be its main task. During

the rule of the progressives, many unregistered religious communities had emerged that supported nationalist agitation [14,297]. The new parliamentary majority rejected requests for registration of these communities, resulting in the dissolution of hundreds of congregations. In 1904, the Chamber of Deputies approved a bill banning the activities of thousands of previously registered communities. Combin anticlerical policy led to a sharp deterioration in relations between France and the Vatican. The Vatican sent a series of notes of protest against the actions of the French government in 1904, when Kombe announced the severance of diplomatic relations with the Vatican. After the resignation of Kombin, a special parliamentary commission headed by Briand prepared a bill on the separation of church and state, adopted in December 1905. According to this law, the Republic guaranteed freedom of conscience and free activity of all religious beliefs. At the beginning of the twentieth century, the guru was hierarchically divided into "the upper (aristocracy, bourgeoisie) and the lower "the way of life of the" upper "differed from the way of life of the" lower". But gradually the upper class (aristocracy, bourgeoisie) lost its monopoly on power, education and culture [14,297]. The leading position in public life began to be occupied by the nascent middle class. This stratum included basically all those who lived by their own labor, on the income of their mental labor, which required special knowledge and a wide culture. These were not only lawyers, doctors, writers of free professions, but also technical intellectuals engineers (on the eve of the war in France there were about 25 thousand engineers), teachers (only in elementary school 125 thousand people), management workers of enterprises belonged. Together with the "new middle class", for the first time in history, the lower classes were also able to enjoy the fruits of development and progress.

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